

AN EVOLVING SYSTEMATIC APPROACH TO UNDERSTANDING THE
UNIQUENESS OF ATHLETES IN THE FIELD OF GYMNASTICS AND ATHLETICS

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Abstract: A systematic approach to solving functional problems involves considering the system through a sequential transition from the general to the specific, when the object under study is isolated from the environment. A systems approach is an approach in which any system (object) is considered as a set of interconnected elements (components) that has an output (goal), input (resources), communication with the external environment, and feedback. Athletics is usually called the queen of sports because it includes the largest number of sports. This is due to the fact that athletics, as a sport, combines natural human locomotion: walking, running, jumping and throwing. At the same time, athletics is a scientific and pedagogical discipline.

Key words: *athletics/ gymnastics/ physical exercise system/ speed/ strength/ flexibility/ endurance.*

РАЗВИВАЮЩИЙСЯ СИСТЕМНЫЙ ПОДХОД К ПОНИМАНИЮ
УНИКАЛЬНОСТИ СПОРТСМЕНОВ ПО СФЕРЕ ГИМНАСТИКИ И ЛЕГКОЙ
АТЛЕТИКИ

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Аннотация: Системный подход к решению функциональных задач предполагает рассмотрение системы путём последовательного перехода от общего к частному, когда исследуемый объект выделяется из окружающей среды. Системный подход это - подход, при котором любая система (объект) рассматривается как совокупность взаимосвязанных элементов, связь с внешней средой, обратную связь. Легкую атлетику принято называть королевой спорта, потому что в нее входит наибольшее число видов спорта. Это обусловлено тем, что легкая атлетика, как вид спорта, объединяет естественные для человека локомоции: ходьбу, бег, прыжки и метания. В то же время легкая атлетика является научно-педагогической дисциплиной.

Ключевые слова: *легкая атлетика/ гимнастика/ система физических упражнений/ быстрота/ сила/ гибкость/ выносливость.*

Athletics is of great importance as an applied sport; with its help, basic physical qualities are developed: strength, speed, endurance, agility, flexibility, which are widely manifested in everyday life and professional activities. In a comprehensive school, athletics is represented by such types as walking, running (short, medium, long distances; relay running; cross-country running), jumping (high, long), throwing (small ball, grenades, shot put).

Model is one of the main categories of the theory of knowledge. In a broad sense, a model is any image (image, map, description, diagram, drawing, graph, plan, etc.) of any object, process or phenomenon, used as their “substitute” or “representative”. A model (Latin “modulus” – measure) is a substitute object for the original object, providing the study of some properties of

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the latter; a simplified representation of the system for its analysis and prediction, to obtain qualitative and quantitative results necessary for making the right management decision. A model is a human-created likeness of the objects being studied: layouts, images, diagrams, verbal descriptions, mathematical formulas, maps, etc.

Athletics is an Olympic sport that includes running, walking, jumping and throwing. Combines the following disciplines: cross-country events, race walking, technical events (jumping and throwing), all-around events, runs (road running) and cross-country.

Modeling is the representation of an object by a model to obtain information about it by conducting experiments with its model. Modeling facilitates the study of an object with the aim of its creation, further transformation and development. There are two main types of modeling: analytical and simulation. To manage business processes (English "Business Process Management", BPM), modern systems use simulation modeling methods. Essentially, any method of scientific research is based on the idea of a model, both theoretical (which uses various kinds of symbolic, abstract models) and experimental, using subject models. Domain models are a set of descriptions that ensure mutual understanding between users: organization specialists and developers. Models are always simpler than real objects, but they allow you to highlight the main thing without being distracted by details. There are mathematical, physical, situational, electrical, and information models.

To achieve the training goal and solve the corresponding problems, numerous means and methods are used. The means is the specific content of the athlete's actions, and the method is the method of action. The main means of training are physical exercises.

For example, mathematical models are used to describe objects and processes of living and inanimate nature and technology, including in physics, biology, economics, and sports.

An information model is a model of an object, process or phenomenon, including information as the main component of the modeled object, process or phenomenon. The most obvious ones from the point of view of using modeling methods are undoubtedly management processes, where appropriate decisions must be made based on the information received. Typically, modeling is used to study an existing system, when it is impractical to conduct a real experiment due to significant financial and labor costs, as well as when it is necessary to analyze the designed system, i.e. which does not yet physically exist in this organization. For a person, an information model is a source of information on the basis of which he forms an image of the real situation. The most obvious ones from the point of view of using modeling methods are undoubtedly management processes, where appropriate decisions must be made based on the information received. Typically, modeling is used to study an existing system, when it is impractical to conduct a real experiment due to significant financial and labor costs, as well as when it is necessary to analyze the designed system, i.e. which does not yet physically exist in this organization. For a person, an information model is a source of information on the basis of which he forms an image of the real situation.

Athletics for children has a lot of advantages, because this sport develops endurance in a child, speed of reaction, strengthens the immune system and promotes proper physical development.

There is no unambiguous concept of a system. In general terms, a system is understood as a set of interconnected elements that form a certain integrity, unity. The process of building a model is a creative procedure that is difficult to formalize. Model representations are abstract

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images of system elements (objects, hardware, software, etc.). Together they allow you to get a fairly complete picture of the system being created.

Athletics is usually called the queen of sports because it includes the largest number of sports. This is due to the fact that athletics, as a sport, combines natural human locomotion: walking, running, jumping and throwing. At the same time, athletics is a scientific and pedagogical discipline. Athletics includes five types of exercises: walking, running, jumping, throwing and various types of all-around events. Each of these types has its own varieties and variants.

In the physical education curricula of universities, athletics is a compulsory subject and occupies an important place in the general system of training specialists. Athletics is characterized by a wide variety of competitive exercises, a significant number of different methods and options for their implementation. It helps to increase the functional capabilities of the body, develop motor qualities, and develop will and character. Walking is a natural way of human movement. Race walking differs from normal walking both in its greater speed and in its unique technique, which ensures significant speed and efficiency of movements. With systematic training in race walking, the activity of the cardiovascular, respiratory and other systems of the body is activated, endurance is developed, and such valuable qualities as perseverance will, perseverance, the ability to endure difficulties, and fight fatigue that inevitably arise during long-term competitions are cultivated.

Running is the basis, the main form of athletics. Usually running is the central part of all competitions. In addition, running is an integral part of many other athletics exercises, such as long jump, high jump, high jump, and javelin throw. Running, depending on its nature, has different effects on the human body. A slow, long run in a park or forest (jogging) has primarily hygienic and health benefits. Fast sprinting helps improve speed and strength qualities, middle and long distance running helps improve endurance, and hurdling helps improve agility and the ability to coordinate movements.

Jumps in athletics are divided according to their purpose into long and high jumps, which are performed from a standing start and from a running start. Currently, standing jumps are not included in the program of official competitions, but are used primarily as a means of training and as tests to determine the level of physical fitness of an athlete. Jumps are performed in various ways. So, you can jump in length by "bending your legs", "bending over" or "scissors", and in height - by "stepping", "rolling", "wave", "flipping", "Fosbury flop". With some methods of performing jumps, there are several options.

Throwing is a speed-strength exercise, the purpose of which is to move projectiles in space to the greatest possible distance. Throwing is characterized by powerful short-term "explosive" efforts. It develops, first of all, strength, improves speed, agility, and coordination of movements. Throwing exercises are classified depending on the nature of the run and the way the projectile is held. From the acceleration of the projectile, a disc, a hammer, a weight (a ball with a loop) is thrown by rotation; shot put and stone put from the jump; from a running start - throwing a spear, grenade, ball. The all-around consists of several types of athletics. The name of a multiathlon is given by the number of events included in it - triathlon, pentathlon, etc. Usually, the types of multiathlon include running, jumping, throwing, which determines the versatile influence that multiathlon training has on the athlete.

All-around results are determined using a special points table. In some cases, special points tables are compiled to determine the results of all-around competitions among schoolchildren.

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